

The Role of Political Education of the Indonesian Youth National Committee (KNPI) In Improving Youth Participation in the Medan City

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ABSTRACT

Political education can be interpreted as a conscious effort to change the process of social socialization of society, so that they understand and live the true values contained in an ideal political system. The success of political education is determined by a clear perspective through two dimensions, a clear picture of the desired ideal political system as well as the actual state of society itself directly. The real political objective is to represent the leaders of the State who can welfare the people. But in fact the world of politics shows more frauds that make political life impressed dilapidated and politics more miserable people seen from some cases of political game that occurred in this country. Therefore it is necessary to improve the political system in Indonesia by preparing the cadres of the nation as the holder of power later. The study was conducted in Medan City on "The Role of Political Education of Indonesian National Youth Committee (KNPI) in Increasing Youth Active Participation in Medan City". The method of analysis used in this research is qualitative research analysis conducted interactively and lasted continuously until complete, so the data is sufficient with the number of respondents 16 respondents. Sampling of respondents was based on probability sampling. From the result of the research, it is found that Indonesian National Youth Committee (KNPI) of Medan City has given role to political education in Medan City and regular meeting, stabilization of member, organization, winning strategy of candidate in election, political insight enlightenment. While the factors that support and hinder the implementation of political education consists of internal and external factors. Internal factors that support include image, figure, and curiosity, while the inhibitor is a source of funds, human resources, knowledge, and pragmatic attitude. External factors that support is religion, while the obstacle is the response of young people in political education.

Keywords: *Role of Youth, Political Education, Indonesian National Youth Committee (KNPI)*

INTRODUCTION

Political socialization consists of two types of activities, namely political education and political indoctrination. Political socialization or political education in the sense of a loose word is a direct part of everyday life, liked or not, known or not, realized or not it is experienced by members of the community both rulers and ordinary people. Political indoctrination is a

unilateral process when the authorities mobilize and manipulate citizens to accept values, norms and symbols that are considered by the ruling party to be ideal and good, through various forums that are full of psychological coercion, and disciplined training (Surbakti, 2010: 150) Countries that adhere to the principle of democracy do not recognize the existence of political indoctrination because they

contradict the principles of democracy, but carry out political education activities. Basically political education is carried out intentionally and a conscious effort planned so that it can cover all aspects of people's lives regardless of the status, position or age of a person and can be carried out by someone who is more experienced or mature towards the next generation. Political education is very contrary to political indoctrination because political education is carried out by formal, informal, or youth organizations concerned directly between the giver and recipient of information so that each individual can know directly the information provided, political education can be carried out by youth organizations to improve someone's active participation without coercing the participation of members because one's active participation is voluntary, while political indoctrination emphasizes the mobilization of the authorities unilaterally so that the community must follow it, this is binding and emphasizes that one must participate whatever the reason.

Political education can be interpreted as a conscious effort to change the process of political socialization of society, so that they understand and fully appreciate the values contained in an ideal political system. The success of political education is determined by a clear perspective through two dimensions, in the form of a clear picture of the ideal political system that is desired and the actual situation of the society itself which can be directly compared with the demands of the ideal political system (Alfian, 1978: 235). The real political goal is to represent state officials who can prosper the people. But in fact the political world shows more cheating that makes political life seem dilapidated and politics is more miserable to the people as seen from several cases of political games that occur in this country. This is also shown by some people who complain, because their lives cannot be prospered by the state. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the political system in Indonesia by

preparing national cadres as holders of power later. One specific method of preparation is to provide the right political education to Indonesia's young generation.

Political education in its nature should not be indoctrinative (formally), because it will cause the young generation of Indonesia to become rigid, fanatical, and narrow-minded. Whereas a quality democracy is a democracy that is capable of realizing the ideals of the state in accordance with the Opening of the 4th paragraph of the 1945 Constitution. This means that by providing the right political education to Indonesia's young generation, we have formed a miniature of state success in various ways. The implementation of political education is very closely related to youth organizations. Youth organizations exist nationally and are formed by a group of Indonesian citizens voluntarily on the basis of the same will and ideals to fight for, defend the political interests of members, society, nation and state, and maintain the integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia based on the Pancasila and Law Basic State of the Republic of Indonesia in 1945 (1945 Constitution). Youth organizations have a very important role in carrying out political education, with these activities a youth organization can increase the active participation of every citizen in a youth organization.

Youth organizations in Indonesia are very diverse, and the number is very large. Each youth organization has a different platform, some of which carry the basis of Islam, nationalism, socialism or struggle. One of the nationalist-based youth organizations in Indonesia is KNPI. The KNPI is very persistent in fighting for the aspirations of the youth and realizing a just, prosperous, inner and prosperous civil society in the Unitary Republic of Indonesia based on Pancasila and always obeying the teachings of religion. The community that embraces religion consists of various elements which are divided into young people and the elderly both women and

men. Youth cannot miss information in politics. Because the flow of political development greatly influences the state and development of the country, so that young people are able to guard the direction of political development. As the next generation and future leaders, adolescents are expected to be able to give their role to politics which is part of a democracy that aims to prosper the people. With participation in a professional and responsible manner by the youth, it is hoped that later it will give new ideas that bring the nation to a better change.

In carrying out an activity will certainly find obstacles in the field, whether it comes from within the organization itself or from outside the organization. Youth need to get an understanding of the real political meaning, not the practical politics practiced by politicians today. The understanding and mindset of youth towards politics must be straightened out, that politics is to meet the needs of the people not to seek power at the expense of the public interest. The political education that will be carried out by the Indonesian Youth National Committee (KNPI) of Medan City encourages researchers to reveal more about the Role of the Indonesian Youth National Committee (KNPI) in carrying out political education to increase youth active participation in a youth organization through research entitled "The Role of Education Politics of the Indonesian Youth National Committee (KNPI) in Increasing Active Participation of Youth in the City of Medan ". Based on the background of the problem, this study has the following objectives: Analyzing the role and form of political education carried out by the Indonesian National Youth Committee (KNPI) in increasing the active participation of youth in Medan City. Analyzing the active participation of youth in carrying out political education carried out by the Indonesian Youth National Committee (KNPI) in Medan City. Analyzing the supporting and inhibiting factors of the Indonesian Youth National Committee

(KNPI) in carrying out political education in increasing the active participation of youth in the City of Medan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Understanding of Politics

Politics comes from the Greek word "policy" which means the city state. Etymologically the word politics is still closely related to political words which mean things related to politics. The word politician means people who pursue things related to politics. Leaders have diverse perspectives on the notion of politics. The following are some definitions of politics according to experts among Miriam Budiardjo. According to him, the notion of political science is the study of politics. Politics is defined as efforts to achieve a good life. Greeks like Plato and Aristoteles call it "En Dam onia or the good life" (good life). Whereas Kosasih Djahiri said that Understanding political science saw power as the core of politics gave birth to a number of theories about how to obtain and implement power. Actually, every individual cannot escape from power, because it affects someone or a group of people who can display behavior as desired by a person or party that influences it.

Definition of Political Education

The concept of political education consists of two key keywords namely education and politics, education is closely related to politics, the relationship of education to politics is very empirical and has been going on for a long time. Education in this case is a process that is deliberately carried out to explore and develop the potential that exists in students so that they have the ability to respond positively to the environment or make changes (knowledge, attitudes and behaviors) that are meaningful to themselves, society and the surrounding environment. (politics) is an attempt to determine the rules that are acceptable to most citizens, to bring people towards a harmonious life together. The effort to reach

the good life involves a variety of activities which include the process of determining the objectives of the system, as well as ways to implement that goal. Society makes decisions about what is the purpose of the political system and this involves the choice between several alternatives and the order of priorities of the objectives that have been determined (Budiardjo, 2008: 15).

Political education is also interpreted as a conscious effort to change the political socialization process of the community so that they understand and appreciate the values contained in an ideal political system that is to be built. The success of political education is determined, among others, by the existence of a clear perspective that can be obtained through two dimensions, namely in the form of a clear picture of the desired political system and reality or the real situation of society itself that can be directly compared with the demands of the ideal political system (Alfian, 1978: 235). Political education is closely related to political socialization, this is because political education with political socialization both provides knowledge to the public about politics either consciously or unconsciously which leads to the attitude of inviting and providing knowledge. Political education is a process of learning and understanding of the rights, obligations and responsibilities of every citizen in the life of the nation and state (Law Number 2 of 2011 concerning Political Parties). Political education is an attempt made intentionally and systematically to form individuals who are aware of the importance of participating in political activities and political personality, in order to be responsible participants.

Political education needs to be given to the younger generation, given the diverse conditions of society, many of which are still in the backwardness and ignorance of politics and education is needed to stimulate people's active participation in the development movement (Kartono, 1989: 3). Political education is essentially part of adult education, this kind of education

clearly does not emphasize the process of cultivation (the cultivation of values that will affect the audience) of individuals as "isolated individuals" in a vacuum but rather emphasize human self realization in a political context. Political education according to Ruslan (in Handoyo 2010) is an effort devoted by educational institutions both formal and non-formal which seek to shape and foster a political personality that is in line with the political culture of the people engaged in these institutions for every citizen the state, establishes and fosters political awareness at all levels of citizens so that they become aware and able to obtain their own awareness, form and foster the ability of political participation actively and participate in solving common problems of society with all possible forms of participation and which lead to change towards better direction.

The Relationship Between Education and Politics

Education and politics are two important elements in the socio-political system in each country, both developed and developing countries. Although education and politics are positioned as two important elements in the socio-political system, they are often studied as separate parts. Of course this is not right because education and politics work hand in hand in the process of forming community characteristics in a country. More than that, each other supports and fills each other. Educational institutions and processes play an important role in shaping the political behavior of society so that it has a large impact on the characteristics of education in a country. From the statement, it can be concluded that there is a close and dynamic relationship between education and politics in each country. This relationship is an empirical reality that has occurred since the beginning of the development of human civilization and is of concern to scientists.

According to M. Sirozi (2010: 1) a clear picture of the relationship between education and politics can be traced in the

Islamic world, where the history of Islamic civilization is marked by the sincerity of scholars and umara in paying attention to the issue of education as an effort to strengthen the group's social position and followers. Furthermore, M. Sirozi cites an analysis from Abdurrasyid (1994) on education in classical Islamic times with conclusions in the history of the development of Islam. Political institutions also colored the style of education developed. The involvement of the authorities in educational activities at that time, according to Rasyid, was not only limited to moral support for students, but also in the fields of administration, finance and curriculum (1994: 3). He wrote the following. It cannot be denied that educational institutions are one of the political constellations. The role played by mosques and madrassas in cementing the political power of the rulers can be seen in history. On the other hand, the dependence on the helping hand of the rulers in an economical way makes these institutions must be in line with the prevailing political nuances.

In Western countries, the study of educational and political relations was initiated by Plato in his book *Republic*. Although it mainly addresses various state issues, the book also discusses the relationship between ideology and state institutions with the aims and methods of education. The following is a profound impression of Allan Bloom (1987: 380) about the *Republic* "For me (*Republic* is) the book on education, because it really explains to me what I am and a teacher, and I have almost always used it to point out what is not teaching for moderation and resignation.

Plato demonstrated in the book that in Hellenistic culture, school is one aspect of life that is related to political institutions. He explained that every culture maintains control over education over elite groups that continuously control political, economic, religious and educational power. Plato describes the dynamic relationship between

educational activities and political activities. Both are like two sides of a coin, it cannot be separated. Although very general and concise, Plato's analysis has laid the groundwork for the study of political relations and education among the next generation of scientists. The relationship between politics and education is manifested in various different forms, according to the characteristics of the socio-political setting where the relationship occurs. The form of the relationship varies from one community to another. In a society, the relationship can be very strong and real and in other societies it can be weak and unreal. The pattern of relations between education and politics in developing countries varies from one community to another. In more primitive societies based on tribal bases (Tribal-based societies) for example, it is common for parents of one tribe to play two roles, as political leaders and as educators. They make important decisions and ensure that these decisions are implemented and implemented. They also prepare young people to enter adult life by teaching them techniques of hunting and fishing, fighting methods and so on. In addition, they also instill in their young generation their beliefs, values and traditions and prepare them to play a political role.

In modern society in general, education is a very important political commodity. Educational processes and institutions have many political aspects and faces, and have several important functions that have an impact on the political system, stability and daily practices. In modern society education is a large area of government responsibility. Public education is political because it is controlled by the government and influences the credibility of the government. Because of the large political nuances of education policies, various political factors that have nothing to do with education also influence how control over education and how education policies are made. As an area of government responsibility, education is often "forced" to

adjust to general administrative patterns and prevailing norms. As a result, public education is funded and controlled by the government as well as the government to finance and control other fields, such as agriculture, health, or social services.

Because of the strong link between the problem of education and politics and other public aspects, every government policy in the field of education generally reflects its views on society and its political beliefs. Each government places different educational priorities, and likes policies that reflect their basic views and interests. From time to time the government makes educational policies on the basis of political considerations. Decisions about education are often influenced by financial factors faced by the government. Schools, universities and public education institutions are the public sectors most affected by the application of the political system. This does not mean that non-government educational institutions are not affected by government decisions and controls. Because in general non-government schools are very dependent on state subsidies, so to get government subsidies, these non-government schools are often required by education authorities to meet the requirements set by the government, such as adjusting the organizational structure of the school, overhauling the curriculum, criteria teacher appointments, fund management procedures, accreditation formats, not using certain textbooks, using certain uniforms, carrying out certain ceremonies and so on. This confirms that education and politics are two things that are closely related and influence each other. In other words, various aspects of education always contain political elements, and vice versa, every political activity has something to do with educational aspects.

Purpose of Political Education

The aim of political education according to Presidential Instruction No. 12 of 1982 concerning Political Education for the Young Generation is to create a young

generation who are aware of the life of the nation and state based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution as an effort to develop Indonesian people as a whole. It aims to provide knowledge to the public to become aware of politics and will gradually develop the talents and interests of someone to participate in the political world and be able to compete positively, critically, creatively and responsibly and fully guided by Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution. "Political education is closely related to national education having two objectives, namely: first, to make the people (individuals, clients, students, and citizens) able to understand the socio-political situation that is full of conflict in a responsible manner and critical of the conflicts that occur. Second, displaying the human role of each individual as a citizen by developing all his talents, potentials and abilities (knowledge, attitude, insight and skills) so that he can actively participate in the political process for the sake of nation and state development. Especially for the younger generation, the goal of political education for the younger generation is: (1) to build a young generation of Indonesians who are politically aware and aware of the life of the nation and state based on the Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution, (2) as an effort to build a complete Indonesian human its manifestation is reflected in a number of traits or personality characteristics of Indonesia "(Kartono, 1989). The purpose of political education is basically to provide knowledge to individuals or groups about how important it is as members of the citizenry to participate in government arrangements and be active in various political lives that exist through small things, for example by becoming party members (cadres), participating vote in general election activities, or participate in campaigning for a political party. Political education can form citizens who have a critical attitude, are active and able to carry out political activities correctly and avoid fraudulent political activities.

Political Participation

The form of participation is very diverse, the form of active participation is closely related to the form of one's political participation, but the participation that will be studied is a form of one's active participation in a political party aimed at young people. Participation is the participation of each individual in a political activity that is using his rights and obligations as a citizen through general elections, being a member or cadre of a political party or just being a fanatical sympathizer for a political party in Indonesia, because by participating someone will become a citizen the truth is by participating in government. This research study focused on young people in participating in a party.

This modern era the ideals of political participation increasingly crystallized and even became part of the concept of political development and modernization. Weiner in Kamarudin, there are two driving factors for the strengthening of political participation. First, the growth of the urban workforce working in the industrial sector which encourages labor organizations. Second, the growth of mass communication due to population development, transportation, communication between urban centers and underdeveloped regions, the spread of newspapers, radio use and so on (Kamarudin, 2003: 168). Both of these factors are influential in the activity of each individual's active participation in direct politics, because one's participation is not only influenced by a particular political party but the environment also influences.

The definition of political participation by Faulks is that political participation is the active involvement of individuals and groups in government processes that have an impact on their lives. This includes the involvement of citizens in making political decisions, directly or indirectly. Political participation is an active process, where a person can be a member of a party or pressure group, but does not play

an active role in the organization. Huntington and Nelson define political participation not only activities carried out by the perpetrators themselves that are intended to influence government decision-making, but also activities that other people outside the actor intended to influence government decision making (Handoyo, 2010: 228). Someone who participates in participation does not have to be a cadre in a political party but being a sympathizer for a political party can be called active participation because he participates in deciding something related to government.

Political Participation Theory

Faulks in Handoyo (2010) proposed three theories of political participation, namely the theory of democratic elitism, rational choice theory and the theory of democratic participation. The theory of democratic elitism with rational choice theory is the theory of instrumentalist participation, because political participation is used as a means to achieve more important goals, while the theory of democratic participation views political involvement as developmental, meaning participation is more than the art of government, but has more goals broad, that is to unite civil society and educate citizens about the art of government.

The theory of democratic participation has an important role in one's activities; because this theory believes that political activism not only benefits participants, but also becomes a more basic foundation for the basic stability sought by political elites. Based on this theory, a citizen can participate in determining the government's decision, a citizen can participate as a member or sympathizer of a political party, this will have an impact on the political party in question, namely increased support from members of the party.

Indicator of Active Political Participation

The indicators underlying the level of participation of community political

parties are the level of education, and gender. Active participation can be carried out with activities that do not take up a lot of time such as voting in general elections, while active political participation is fully that is participating in political activities such as being party leaders, members of political parties, or becoming cadres in a political party.

The forms of political participation according to Rush and Althof, (1990: 124) are as follows: (1) occupying political or administrative positions, (2) seeking political or administrative positions, (3) active membership of a political organization, (4) passive membership a political organization, (5) active membership of a quasi-political organization (quasi political), (6) passive membership of a quasi-political organization (quasi political), (7) participation in public meetings, demonstrations and so on (8) participation in discussions informal politics general interest in politics, (9) voting (voting), (10) apathi total.

These forms of political participation are from the lowest form of participation to the peak of participation, namely by holding political or administrative positions, one's participation in political activities does not have to go through all levels of participation because one's participation cannot be imposed by anything because we adhere to democratic principles, so someone can freely choose activities or participate in various political activities. Active participation (doing real) has influence and strength, because it can also participate in monitoring activities governing society and the state (Kartono, 1989: 76). These forms of political participation can be used as an indicator of someone's political participation, some in the form of active participation or passive participation, in research conducted by the author specializing in the active participation of young people towards the KNPI in Medan.

The purpose of political participation is to influence government decision making.

Therefore, the activities must be aimed at and have an impact on the centers where the decision is taken. Analyzing a person's level of participation we need to distinguish two sub-dimensions (a) the scope, or proportion of a population category that is defined, which involves special participation activities, and (b) intensity, or size, duration, and significance of activities specifically for the political system. A particular country, most of the population may participate in elections, an act of small intensity, some with fewer in number may participate in campaign activities, and some with fewer numbers may play a continuous role individually and through organizations in an effort to influence government decisions (Huntington, 1994: 16).

Understanding Youth

Youth are individuals who when viewed physically are experiencing emotional development, so that youth is a development human resource both for now and in the future. Basically emotional young people tend to be higher and sensitive to problems that occur, especially those concerning their self-esteem, in the political sphere young people are often apathetic because they have not fully been able to give trust to the government. Youth in terms of ideological politics, youth is the successor of the previous generation in this case between the ages of 17-30 years (Inpres Number 12 of 1982 concerning Political Education for the Young Generation) was determined as the recognition of the political rights of youth in national and religious life. This was seen in his participation in general elections at the age of 17 years.

Youth is the optimal life span. At that time the physical maturity, feelings, and reason and have a high sensitivity to the surrounding environment. Critical thoughts and strategic actions are highly coveted by the surrounding community. Youth are agents of social change (social of change agents) who have a heavy burden to reach

change and do concrete actions in order to save generations (Setiawan, 2009: 63 & 71).

Youth are agents and leaders of change, young people cannot put down the ideals of the nation and their future in a handful of national elites who only take momentary gains from power. Youth who are relatively clean from various cases and interests must be counted as expensive assets for the glory of Indonesia in the future (Setiawan, 2009: 73). The participation of youth in political activities is very necessary to provide new colors and changes that lead to developments towards the future of the Indonesian nation and not only utilized by political elites who take advantage and momentary power.

The position of youth is very important in the level of bureaucracy because the presence of young people who participate in politics can provide significant changes with creative and critical thoughts. "Youth participation and independence in the state is an expression of citizenship which indicates that a country is practicing democracy, both economically, politically and socially. The process of independence and youth participation is a strategic movement that needs to be encouraged continuously to lead to the formation of civil society. This is necessary because of the atmosphere of democracy in Indonesia, in this case the building of relations between the state and the community has not clearly involved youth "(Setiawan, 2009: 101)

Indonesian Youth National Committee (KNPI)

The Indonesian Youth National Committee (KNPI) was formed on 23 July 1973 in Jakarta as a national level communication forum between the younger generation. As Chairman of the KNPI David Napitupulu was elected. The youths who joined the KNPI have issued a declaration, which among other things contains that Indonesian youth are heirs and successors of the ideals of the Indonesian nation and are determined to develop the Youth Oath based on Pancasila, the 1945 Constitution, and the

Broad Guidelines of the State, and intend to participate in efforts to accelerate development.

The KNPI which is a product of corporate policy is certainly not easy to let go of the logic of coaching or control. This guidance is very conducive for the development of a culture of blessing. Because without the blessing and support of the coach, it will have political meaning and nil. This blessing culture has very dominant implications. The orientation of youth activities that possess a critical character will be confined (co-optation), so that it is unable to put pressure on the government in channeling its political aspirations. Its function is only a witness and legitimacy for the formalization of the hammer beats that have been decided before. The policy-making forum loses its dynamics, because more is controlled by remote forces behind the scenes. To get blessing and fulfill his political interests, for activities absolutely necessary political patronage. The leader is like a political client who seeks his patron who functions as a protector, as well as a boosting force for his political mobility, while the patron (the ruler) of the client becomes an arm of his hand, to carry out political guidance or control.

Purpose of the Indonesian Youth National Committee (KNPI)

Based on the 2015 Congress of the Indonesian National Youth Committee (KNPI) in Jayapura Papua that in the KNPI Articles of Association article 3 CHAPTER II concerning the objectives of the KNPI are:

1. The realization of the unity and unity of Indonesian youth for the sake of the establishment of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.
2. The creation of Indonesian youth who have intellectual abilities, noble character, and have professional expertise, in order to guarantee the continuity of national development.
3. The empowerment of all potentials of Indonesian youth in various dimensions

of the life of the nation and state in order to accelerate the realization of a just, prosperous and prosperous Indonesian society based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution.

Function of the Indonesian Youth National Committee (KNPI)

Based on the 2015 Congress of the Indonesian National Youth Committee (KNPI) in Jayapura Papua that in the Articles of Association KNPI article 7 CHAPTER IV concerning the functions of the KNPI, namely:

1. As a container for Indonesian youth pluralism in order to improve the quality of life of the people, nation and state in order to accelerate efforts to achieve national goals
2. As a laboratory for Indonesian youth cadres in order to develop the potential of youth who are nationally minded, independent and responsible, in order to ensure the regeneration process of the nation's future sustainability.
3. As a forum for Indonesian youth struggle in order to increase the degree, standard of living, status and social welfare, in order to accelerate the creation of a just, prosperous and prosperous society.

MATERIALS & METHODS

The research location is the place of research used to carry out research, making it easier for someone to know the place of research, which is carried out in the city of Medan. The time of the study was conducted in October - December 2017. Medan is one of the most important mass base of the Indonesian Youth National Committee (KNPI) in North Sumatra, where the KNPI address of Medan City is on Jl. Nibung II No. 14 Petisah sub-district, Kec. Medan Petisah Medan City North Sumatra Province. This study uses qualitative research methods, Bogdan and Tylor define qualitative methodology as a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written or oral words from

people and observable behavior (Moloeng, 2002: 3). Through qualitative methods, this study can provide an overview of the Role of the Indonesian Youth National Committee (KNPI) in Implementing Political Education to Enhance Youth Active Participation in the City of Medan.

Informants are people who are used to provide information about the situation and background conditions of the study, he must have a lot of experience on the background of research (Moleong 2006: 132). Therefore, an informant must really know or the actors who are directly involved with the research problem. And choosing an informant must be seen as not just competing to present it. As already stated that the selection of informants is a very important thing so that it must be done carefully, because this study examines the Paran of KNPI political education to increase the active participation of youth in the city of Medan. So the researcher decides the first informant or the most appropriate and appropriate key informant is the chairman and secretary of the Medan City KNPI. The focus of the research is detailed into several research indicators as follows:

1. The Role of the Indonesian Youth National Committee (KNPI) includes: background in the implementation of KNPI political education, the process of implementing political education, the results of the implementation of political education, the implementation of the implementation of political education. The form of political education includes: the form or model of political education activities carried out by the KNPI, the material, methods, time and place of implementation of the Medan KNPI DPD political education in increasing youth active participation.
2. Active Political Partissive Youth in Medan City has indicators in the form of education, gender and age. The participation of youth in participating in political activities, for example being an

organizational leader / party, member or being a cadre in various organizations.

3. Supporting and inhibiting factors, including: internal factors and external factors KNPI in carrying out political education. Internal factors include: image sources, figures, sources of funds, human resources. External factors include: curiosity, religion, youth response, knowledge, pragmatic attitude.

The research indicators can facilitate researchers to answer the problem formulation and facilitate the implementation of research in the field, according to the research focus and indicators of the research, the researcher carried out the research entitled *The Role of the Indonesian Youth National Committee (KNPI) in Implementing Political Education to Increase Youth Active Participation in Medan City*.

Data sources are the subject from which data is obtained (Arikunto, 2006: 129). Qualitative research on the data collection process is carried out in various sources, settings and methods, in this study the data sources used are as follows:

1. Primary data sources are data sources that directly provide data to data collectors. The data source of this study came from the chairperson, functionaries, members of the Medan KNPI DPD, young people who were members and not yet members of the Medan City KNPI DPD.
2. Secondary data sources are sources that indirectly provide data to researchers originating from data, documents or archives related to political education activities carried out by the Medan City KNPI DPD. The data obtained by the researcher is a document of the organizational structure of the KNPI DPD in Medan.

Data collection techniques used by researchers in this study include interviews (interviews), questionnaires (questionnaires), observations (observations), and a combination of the three.

1. Interview

Interviews are conversations with a specific purpose, the conversation is carried out by both parties, namely the interviewer (interviewer) who asks questions and the interviewee (interviewee) who provides answers to the question. (Moleong, 2002: 135). The interview was conducted by the researcher with the chairman of the Medan KNPI DPD regarding the role of the Indonesian Youth National Committee (KNPI) in carrying out political education on youth, forms of political education carried out and supporting and inhibiting factors for the implementation of political education. The researchers then conducted interviews with the KNPI DPD secretary Medan City and members of the Medan KNPI DPD with the same material and interview material, because the chairman and functionaries have a role to succeed in political education being carried out, in order to increase the support and active participation of the youth in the Medan KNPI DPD. Interviews conducted by researchers, carried out face-to-face directly with the informants and provide guidance on interviews with informants so that things that are less clear can be explained in writing, and answers that verbally given by informants to researchers written by researchers in detail while deepening the answers that have been given by the informant.

2. Observation

Data collection through observation method is one of the main methods besides interviews. Observation can be done in several ways, namely observers actively participate (participatory observation), ie researchers are directly involved in participating in carrying out activities carried out by data sources so that the data obtained is more complete by following the daily activities carried out by informants. Obvious observation or disguised observation is done by the researcher frankly and stated to the data source that he was conducting research so that the data sources knew the research process from the

beginning to the end (Sugiyono, 2008: 228). The observations carried out by the researchers were straightforward observations by following the process of political education carried out by the KNPI DPD in Medan. Observation activities carried out by researchers following political education activities carried out in Medan City KNPI DPD. During the observations carried out the researchers were at the house of the father of the Medan KNPI DPD secretary.

3. Documents

Document study is a complement to the method of observation and interviews in qualitative research. The document is a record of events that have passed. Documents can be in the form of writing, pictures, photographs or works of art and others (Sugiyono, 2008: 240), documents used by researchers are photos of the Medan KNPI DPD education activities, namely regular meetings, youth participation and sympathizers of the KNPI in giving their voting rights.

4. Triangulation

Triangulation is defined as a technique of collecting data that is combining the various techniques of collecting data and existing data sources. Data collection using triangulation, researchers collect data while testing the credibility of data, namely checking the credibility of data with various data collection techniques and various data sources. The researcher compared the data that had been obtained from the informants by looking directly at the facts that existed either through documentation, or observations made whether they were the same or there were differences.

Analysis of the data used in qualitative research is carried out interactively and continues continuously to completion, so that the data is sufficient. Activities in data analysis are data condensation, data display, drawing and verification conclusions according to Miles and Huberman (2014) Qualitative data analysis.

1. Data Condensation

Data Condensation is often used to summarize, choose, the main things, focus on important things, look for themes and patterns, discard unnecessary ones so that they provide a clear picture and make it easier for researchers to carry out further data collection. Data Condensation carried out by researchers is to choose and use data that is truly in accordance with the problem formulation in the study, which is in accordance with the role of the KNPI in carrying out political education to increase active participation of young people, a form of political education carried out by Medan KNPI DPD in carrying out political education and the factors that support and hinder the implementation of the Medan KNPI DPD political education.

2. Data Display (Data Presentation)

Data display or presentation of data is to show all certain descriptions of the results of research, so that research conducted by researchers can be understood thoroughly and master the data that has been obtained. The process of presenting data carried out by researchers in this study is that researchers present data on research results that have been obtained by researchers in conducting research.

3. Drawing and Verification Conclusion

Drawing and verification Conclusion is the process of drawing conclusions from all the data that has been collected in the research process that has been carried out, so that the results of the research that has been carried out draw conclusions or final verification. At this stage the researcher draws conclusions from the results of the research and discussion that have been carried out so that the conclusions from the research results that have been carried out clearly and precisely in accordance with the research data obtained regarding the role, form and supporting factors as well as inhibiting the implementation of Medan KNPI DPD political education.

SWOT Analysis Techniques

According to Rangkuti (2005), SWOT analysis is one method for

describing conditions and evaluating a problem, project or business concept based on internal (inside) factors and external (external) factors, namely Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities and Threats that will be carried out. SWOT analysis only describes situations that occur not as problem solvers. The SWOT analysis consists of four factors, namely:

- 1) Strengths are the strength conditions found in an organization, project or business concept that exist. The strength analyzed is the factor found in the body of the organization, project or business concept itself.
- 2) Weakness is a condition of weakness found in the organization, project or business concept that exists. Weaknesses analyzed are factors found in the body of an organization, project or business concept itself.
- 3) Opportunities are conditions for opportunities to develop in the future that occur. Conditions that occur are opportunities from outside the organization, the project or business concept itself for example competitors, government policies, environmental conditions.
- 4) Threats are a threatening condition from the outside. This threat can disrupt the organization, project or business concept itself.

This study consisted of three stages, namely the preparation stage, the stage of conducting research, and data analysis.

Pre-research or preparation stages

The activities carried out were research designs and research instruments, so that before conducting research the researchers had an idea of what was done during the study. At this stage the researcher composes a research proposal and prepares a research instrument design for the smooth implementation of research in the field.

Stage of conducting research

Researchers go directly to the field to make observations, collect data and analyze data that has been obtained in the field. At this stage the researcher carries out

research that starts from meeting the informant to convey the purpose and objectives carried out by the researcher, determine the timing of the proper interview, so as not to interfere with the informant's activities in the busyness of each informant.

Stage of writing a research report

The researcher compiles a report to report the results of the research that has been carried out at the stage of the research. The research report is written in the current format and rules and in accordance with the data from the research results in the field.

RESULT

The Role of Political Education of the Indonesian Youth National Committee (KNPI) in Enhancing Youth Active Participation in Medan City.

The work program implemented by the Medan City KNPI DPD is different from the North Sumatra Province KNPI DPD. This is because the scope and level of position are different. The work program of the Medan City KNPI DPD was adapted to the circumstances in the Medan KNPI DPD environment with the community, especially young people, one of which was political education.

Based on the results of the interview with El Adrian Shah, SE as chairman of the KNPI Medan City DPD regarding the views on political education and the background of the implementation of political education towards young people, he said: "Political education is very necessary so that cadres really know and understand the principle and the aim of the Indonesian Youth National Committee (KNPI), indeed to face the future it is necessary to prepare leaders who can be accountable, have good dedication, morality, faith and piety to prepare leaders. So, political education really needs to be more especially for young people as the relay of the nation's struggle" (Interview December 8, 2017).

This means that political education is very important to give to cadres, especially young people as the relay of the

nation's struggle so that it can be used to prepare responsible leaders, have good dedication, morality, faith and piety. It is through this political education that young people will truly know and understand the principles and objectives of the KNPI DPD in Medan.

Medan City DPD KNPI functionaries in participating in political education are instructions that must be carried out, the Medan City DPD KNPI secretary Khairuddin Aritonang, ST stated as follows: "The field responsible is education, because in functionaries there is a division of education into two, namely education in general and specifically in the field of political education, the field of education has the duty not only to carry out political education, but also to participate in registering participants participating in political education, looking for tutors or resource persons to fill political education, providing places and accommodations to support the smooth implementation of political education "(Interview December 6, 2017).

The education sector is divided into two parts, namely the field of general education and the field of political education, general education has a religious element, while political education refers to the provision of knowledge of matters relating to politics. The field of education does not only carry out political education, but arranges designs, stages, starting from finding or determining speakers to the implementation of political education.

Political education carried out by the KNPI DPD in Medan is not only for members of the KNPI DPD, but covers the entire general public and young people. Based on the results of an interview with El Adrian Shah, SE, he said: "All the KNPI DPD City Medan functionaries said that anyone could participate in the implementation of political education from the Medan KNPI DPD because it could add members and sympathizers" (interview on December 6 2017). The stages of the implementation of the KNPI DPD Medan

City political education began with the provision of information to the general public, the provision of information provided through short messages sent to all members of the Medan City KNPI DPD, including young people and through information directly to political education participants given by family members or relatives of DPD KNPI City Medan functionaries. After the information was given, then the Medan City DPD KNPI opened registration for political education participants and conducted an evaluation or screening of participants who were truly convinced of their participation in the United Development Party. The process and stages of political education carried out by Medan City KNPI DPD as expressed by Salman Farisi as a member of the Medan City KNPI DPD "the process of implementing political education is carried out with enlightenment and appreciation" (Interview on 15 December 2017).

Political education carried out by the Medan City KNPI DPD was carried out through enlightenment and appreciation in the hope that young people would be more interested and be able to participate in various political activities through the KNPI. Enlightenment in this case is to provide a bright spot on the importance of participating in political activities, while appreciation is the deepening of the importance of participating in political activities so that they can add insight into politics. Political education was carried out by the KNPI DPD of Medan City through speakers who came from the higher level KNPI administrators, as explained by El Adrian Shah, SE "The speaker who gave Medan KNPI DPD political education that was from the higher level KNPI administrators, for example The Medan KNPI DPD which carries out political education, the speakers come from the North Sumatra DPD KNPI, besides that it comes from Medan DPD KNPI functionaries who have higher positions, political education is also given by the KPU in the lead up to elections regarding general

election techniques” (Interview on December 8, 2017).

Forms of Political Education Implemented by the KNPI in Improving Youth Active Participation in Medan City

Form of Political Education

Many ways and strategies are used to carry out political education. The success of the implementation of political education is inseparable from the form of political education and methods used to attract young people. Based on the results of the interview with El Adrian Shah, SE, he said "political education is delivered with accompanying humorous elements, education concerning

arts, question and answer, regular meetings, discussions, strengthening members, party organizations, strategies for winning candidates in elections, and other meetings" (Interview on December 8, 2017).

Medan City KNPI provides political education with various forms and methods of delivery, including: the delivery of political education accompanied by humorous elements, education related to the arts, question and answer. Routine meetings are held through discussion and question and answer sessions carried out by El Adrian Shah, SE with strategy material and increased knowledge of members through the delivery of aspirations from political education participants.

Table 1. The Form of Political Education of the KNPI DPD in Medan City

No	Name of activity	Time Implementation	Interviewees	Information
1	Meeting Routine	Every Sunday first on each month	Chairperson and Coordinator That part in accordance with the material	Regular meetings are carried out on an Idharoh (tour) in the house of the administrator and members Medan City KNPI
2	Stabilization Members and The Medan KNPI DPD Organization	<i>Incidental</i>	Chairperson of Medan City KNPI DPD and Management	Strengthening members and organizations for Maintaining Constituents and Convincing Young People to remain in the scope of the KNPI
3	<i>Conditional</i>	Chairperson, as well as a member of the Medan KNPI DPD	The recitation consists of Various forms include general recitation.	Public Recitation
4	Enlightenment Insights Politics	Anytime adjusted With needs especially from youth	Functionaries Medan City KNPI DPD	Provide a bright point about the importance of participating in activities Politics so that Young People Have a view of politics

Youth Participation in Political Education

Participation is taking part in participating in an activity. In words that are broader, participation in essence is the participation of a person or group of people in a larger activity. Participation only has meaning if accompanied by a sense of responsibility by those who take part in the activity. The Chinese community stated that they had already received the process of socializing political education. As a KNPI member in Medan City, he received political education while attending school activities, from Citizenship Education subjects and Intra-School Student Organizations (OSIS). Some people stated that political education had been obtained

by participating in cultural and religious activities. Like getting a counseling from both the Kelurahan and the Mayor candidates who conducted a meeting with Medan KNPI members who had participated actively in the Medan City Election by directly voting at the polling station (TPS) with a good attendance rate. In addition there are factors that make Medan KNPI members have an active participation attitude, namely the sympathetic feeling of Medan City KNPI members to one of the candidates or one of the mayor pairs that they hope to lead. The participation of some Medan City KNPI members to be part of a successful team formed a political dynamic in the government. This dynamic can be

seen from the heterogeneity of the culture of Indonesian society that is united in politics.

The Supporting and Inhibiting Factors of KNPI in Implementing Political Education to Enhance Youth Active Participation in Medan City.

Internal factors

Internal factors are factors originating from the party itself which can support and hinder the implementation of political education carried out by the Medan City KNPI DPD.

Internal Factors of Supporting Organizations

a. Image

The impression or image of the KNPI as an organization has been widely known to the entire community, so that almost everyone knows the KNPI City of Medan. Based on the results of the interview with Tatang Admaja, he said that "the supporting factor is that Image KNPI has been widely known to the public" (Interview on 12 December 2017)

b. Figure

Figure is one of the important factors in determining and supporting a particular activity, as expressed by Arifin "who supports is the presence of people's representatives as well as the chairman in the Medan City KNPI DPD" (Interview on 15 December 2017). The figure is inseparable from the family figure, because the family is the closest person who has an important role in providing information and support for someone, such as participating in political education carried out by the Medan KNPI DPD. The family has a very important role in supporting the implementation of political education, because from family members, young people can be invited to join the party and obtain information directly regarding the implementation of the Medan KNPI DPD political education.

c. Curiosity

The external factor of the party that supports the implementation of the Medan KNPI DPD political education. Based on the

results of an interview with El Adrian Shah, SE he said "the external factors that support that come from their enthusiasm and curiosity about knowledge about politics" (Interview on December 8, 2017). El Adrian Shah, SE statement: "the supporting factor is the curiosity of participants in political education" (Interview on 15 December 2017). Young people's curiosity towards politics is an external party factor that supports it because it can lead to their curiosity and enthusiasm for participating in activities carried out by the KNPI. Another opinion according to Ardiansyah is: "the supporting factor is the broader insight into politics that will be owned by the community, especially young people" (Interview on 15 December 2017). The benefits obtained by young people and the community after participating in political education, namely having a broad insight into political views in the future, so that they can think of appropriate steps and strategies in politics.

Internal Factors of the Party That Are Inhibiting

Internal party factors that hinder the implementation of political education activities include:

a) Source of funds

The source of funds is very important in supporting the success or failure of the implementation of political education carried out by the Medan City KNPI DPD. Based on the results of interviews with Ardiansyah, he said "the source of funds used by the Medan KNPI DPD comes from membership fees, assistance from board members who are in the Medan KNPI DPD while those from members are contributions of five thousand rupiah each month at the time of implementation routine collection" (Interview on 15 December 2017).

b) Human Resources

The ability and personality of each person has the characteristics and differences between one person and another. This is something natural because we cannot impose and equate one's knowledge

according to our abilities. Based on the results of an interview with El Adrian Shah, SE, he said "Human resources are one of the inhibiting factors for the implementation of political education because they are beginner voters so that they are directly involved in political life" (Interview on December 8, 2017).

Young people are still unstable voters in receiving political education, because they are only involved in political activities for the first time besides the influence of the surrounding environment is one of the influences on someone to jump into politics or not. Based on the observations of the researchers, the implementation of the Medan KNPI DPD political education, during the recitation the number of participants who participated was very large because it was general, but not all participants paid close attention, while many regular education participants on December 5 2017 did not pay attention the material presented by Drs.Sutikno with 33 participants due to unfavorable weather.

c) Knowledge

A person's knowledge in accepting and knowing a subject matter such as politics, will vary from person to person. Based on the interview with Ardiansyah, "there are obstacles, namely because of the demands of work and lack of knowledge in politics" (Interview on 15 December 2017). Job demands are constraints that cannot be forced, unless they voluntarily participate in political education, and lack of political knowledge greatly influences the success of political education carried out by the KNPI. Based on the results of interviews with young people, Danang revealed that "politics is less important and complicated than the news is back and forth, there is no clarity" (Interview on December 10, 2017). The notion of the importance of politics is increasingly emphasizing that young people's knowledge of politics is still low so they are apathetic towards politics. Lack of awareness of the importance of politics, making politics considered an insignificant

thing so they will tend to be passive in politics.

d) Pragmatic attitude

Based on the results of the interview with El Adriansyah, SE he said "the attitude of pragmatism youth, they want to take part in political education activities when they get something they get" (Interview on 8 December 2017). Pragmatic is an attitude that is often encountered in young people but not all have a pragmatic attitude, young people will take political education if they get something in the sense of getting a reward, but not all of them are young men who voluntarily follow it.

External factors

External factors are factors that come from outside the party that can support and respect the implementation of political education from the KNPI DPD in Medan.

Supporting Organization External Factors

a) Religion

Indonesia has a majority of Muslims who are spread throughout the archipelago, Islam can be one of the factors supporting political parties in carrying out activities such as political education carried out by the Medan City KNPI DPD, based on the results of interviews with Sugiyana as follows "supporting factors are citizens a majority Muslim community" (Interview on December 13, 2017).

External Factors that Hinder Demographics
The inhibiting external factors include:

b) Young People's Response

Young people in responding to the results of political education activities carried out are very diverse. Based on the results of the interview with Tatang Admaja, his response was "sometimes I don't understand the implementation of political education and political activities but I still support the KNPI" (Interview on 15 December 2017). The response from young people regarding lack of understanding in politics was lack of understanding in politics, although they did not understand politics but still supported the KNPI.

Even though young people supported and participated in the United Development Party even became a Mabur success team, but there were still young people who did not participate in activities carried out by the United Development Party and even tended to be passive. When becoming a member of a successful team is when the general election approaches, so young people begin to actively participate in party activities, for ordinary days participating in politics tend to be passive.

SWOT Analysis in Supporting and Inhibiting Factors

The identification of internal and external factors formulated in an effort to analyze the role strategy of the Indonesian National Youth Committee (KNPI) political education, can be seen as follows:

Internal and External Factor Analysis

1. Strength

- Having supporting human resources
- Have a good figure and image in the community
- Have curiosity in the community

2. Weaknesses

- Lack of cooperation between youth organizations

- Weak recruitment system within the organization
- Lack of funding sources within the organization

3. Opportunities

- Opportunities for the Young Generation / Students to take part in the field of politics are wide open, both in the Supra Structure and Political Infrastructure in various levels of the Government. Especially in the Political Structure Supra, the opportunity is through recruitment with formal requirements based on the level of education and experience (Career System).

4. Threats

- The biggest challenge for the Young Generation / Students to enter the world of politics comes from itself.
- Today there is unfair competition between the Politics of Identity and the Politics of Modernity.
- Globalization has made the world seem to lose its boundaries, but ironically it is precisely because of this that the Politics of Identity is getting stronger.

Table 2. SWOT and TOWS Matrix

Internal	Strength (S)	Weaknesses (W)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ø Having supporting human resources Have a good figure and image in the community Curiosity in the community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of cooperation between youth organizations Weak recruitment system within the organization Lack of funding sources within the organization
External	Opportunities (O)	Threats (T)
	S + O	W + O
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Improve and develop education for young people Strive for supervision of political education towards young people. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Building cooperation between all elements of youth to jointly develop political education for young people. Strive for publication of young people to the wider community
	S + T	W + T
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Seek the development of adequate political education for the youth in the city of Medan. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Seek knowledge and awareness of youth towards politics in the city of Medan.

Source: Research 2017

By doing a SWOT analysis is the right tool to find problems from four different sides, where the application is how strengths are able to take advantage of the opportunities that exist, then how to overcome weaknesses that prevent profits, then how strengths are able to deal with existing threats, and finally is how to overcome weaknesses that are able to make threats become real or create a new threat. With the interconnection of these four factors, this analysis makes it easy to realize the objectives of the Medan City KNPI DPD. Therefore, youth organizations must be able to face global challenges as a whole to achieve an organizational goal.

DISCUSSION

The KNPI DPD of Medan City carried out political education running for life, especially in childhood. He developed through family, school, workplace, experience as an adult, religious organization, and political party towards the community, especially young people, so that they knew, understood and participated in political activities through the KNPI, this was where the organization played its role as a means of political education (Djakfar, 2009: 42). The Medan KNPI has carried out political education to community members, especially young people. The openness of the Medan KNPI DPD in providing information on the implementation of political education will support the smoothness and increase the number of participants in political education, so that they can add members and support. Today's political education is strongly supported by the availability and ease of access to information, this will further increase public awareness about the world of politics. The easier it is to access information on young people in obtaining information on the implementation of political education, the more participants participate in political education. The condition increasingly benefited the Medan City KNPI, because many political education participants made the Medan City KNPI increasingly known

to the public, especially young people and to maintain the constituents of the KNPI.

A particular country, the majority of its population participates in an election, an act of small intensity, some with fewer numbers, participating in campaign activities, and some with fewer numbers by playing a continuous role individually through an organization. Organization in an effort to influence government decisions (Huntington, 1994: 16). The form of voting support or giving voting rights to the KNPI in the election of mayor and deputy mayor of the field, following the campaign, following the activities carried out by the Medan City KNPI DPD was a form of active participation of youth in the KNPI, because they contributed to activities carried out by the KNPI voluntarily. The active participation of young people in the KNPI DPD of Medan City was shown from Arifn who held the position of secretary in the KNPI Medan City DPD, participated in the campaign and gave voting rights to PPP during the 2015 election of mayor and deputy mayor.

The form of political education carried out by the Medan KNPI DPD has similarities with the media of political education according to Surbakti, (2010: 150) the form or model of political education carried out through course activities, leadership training, discussion, and participation in various meeting forums. Besides that, the form of political education carried out by the Medan KNPI DPD was the strategy of winning candidates in general elections and strengthening members and party organizations.

The way of delivering political education used by the KNPI DPD in Medan includes:

1. The delivery of political education accompanied by humorous elements, the delivery of political education material carried out in a relaxed manner and interspersed with humorous (joking) because with this matter the delivery of material is not tense and can be accepted by political education participants.

2. Education concerning art, educational material that is focused on the development and preservation of arts owned by the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia in general. The implementation can be carried out in accordance with the needs and at any time can be implemented.
3. Presentation, is presenting the main issues related to politics and containing KNPI elements which were carried out simultaneously at the routine meeting held by the Medan City KNPI DPD.
4. Question and answer and discussion, question and answer is an activity carried out between the giver and recipient of political education or among fellow political education participants to provide further understanding of politics, while discussion is an activity carried out to discuss and solve a political problem and a current problem developing in Indonesia. The implementation of question and answer and discussion can be carried out at any time, by visiting the house of the chairman of the Medan KNPI DPD and during regular meetings.

The implementation of political education carried out by the Medan KNPI DPD, through several forms as follows:

Regular meetings, regular meetings are held on the first Friday of each month which are attended by all functionaries, with different material each week.

a) Enlightenment of political insights is to shed some light on the importance of participating in political activities so that young people have a forward-looking view of developing politics.

b) Stabilization of party members and organizations is carried out at any time adjusted to the needs of functionaries, party members and all sympathizers covering young people.

There are scheduled political education and conditional or incidental ones, because the implementation of political education is not always carried out continuously, but adjusted to the situation and needs of

members and young people, the reason is to avoid boredom and boredom of political education participants in participating in the activities carried out and avoiding very large budget expenditures that can hinder the development and existence of the party.

The implementation of the function of political education is carried out through various means, namely mass media, lectures, information, upgrading and some of them (Djakfar, 2009: 42). This is in accordance with the lecture and information activities through the enlightenment of political insights from the DPD KNPI Medan City is part of the form of political education that has been carried out, by giving direction and material delivered through lectures so that there will be discussion and question and answer among political education participants.

Political education carried out by the Medan City KNPI DPD has determined the time and place of implementation that has been agreed upon between functionaries and members. The time for the implementation of political education is scheduled and there are those that are tailored to the needs, duration of time used is approximately 2-3 hours, while the place used is using the Idharoh system (around) and rotating at the boarding house and branch of Medan DPD KNPI and adjusting types of political education activities carried out.

The presence of board members domiciled in the city of Medan and being the chairman of the Medan KNPI DPD, can increase public and youth trust in the Medan KNPI DPD, because they can convey their aspirations directly to their representatives, while those that hinder the implementation of political education include funding sources and human resources, because both of these things can hinder the implementation of the Medan KNPI DPD political education. The majority of Medan City residents are Muslim, Islam, this is the added value of the Medan City KNPI in increasing the support and participation of young people in attending the Medan KNPI DPD political education, religion as a

source of spiritual power as well as a source of awareness of meaning, essence and the purpose of human life, the KNPI argues that qualified Indonesian people are people who are politically conscious so that the KNPI intends to realize the development of political democracy because it relates to the determination of national development policies that concern the lives of many people (Kamarudin, 2003: 68).

The pragmatic attitude that still exists in young people makes politics considered an insignificant thing. Young people are still volatile voters and tend to be apathetic towards politics, so young people will be passive in politics. Kamarudin, (2003: 95) the pattern of political participation is shown through a high and low level of political awareness and political trust, basically determined by at least three main factors, namely the level of education, the level of economic life, and the system. Pragmatic attitude is an attitude that is often found in young people, they will take political education if they get something in the sense of reward, but not all of them are young men who voluntarily follow it. The pragmatic attitude of political education participants held by the KNPI DPD in Medan, so that people tend to be passive in participating in political education or activities carried out by the Medan KNPI DPD

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the discussion, conclusions can be drawn as follows:

That the role of the Indonesian National Youth Committee (KNPI) in carrying out political education is through the form of political education such as routine meetings, strategies for winning candidates in elections, stabilization and organizations. The field responsible for implementing political education is the field of education, which is divided into two parts, namely the field of general education and the field of political education. The field of education does not only carry out political education, but is responsible for

drafting, stages, finding or determining speakers until the implementation of political education. Political education carried out by the Medan City KNPI DPD on young people, because young people are the holders of the nation's struggle for war. Whereas the form of political education carried out by the Medan KNPI DPD included: regular meetings, strengthening of members, organizations, strategies for winning candidates in elections, enlightenment of political insights. The method of delivery used includes the delivery of political education accompanied by humorous elements, political education concerning the arts, discussion, question and answer, and others.

1. The active participation of youth in carrying out political education carried out by the Indonesian National Youth Committee (KNPI) in Medan City is very large and varied including the presence of young people during the implementation of political education. In addition to the presence of Youth in political education, young people are very active in asking questions and giving positive inputs in political education in the city of Medan.
2. Factors that support and hinder the implementation of political education consist of internal and external factors. Supporting internal factors include image, figure, and curiosity, while the obstacles are sources of funds, human resources, knowledge, and pragmatic attitudes. Supporting external factors are religion, while the obstacle is the response of young people in taking political education.

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